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ROLE AND ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY IN THE SPECIALTY CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

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Annotation. This article describes an overview of the mathematical model of the circulatory system for the cardiovascular system via BITalino and provides a basis for the mathematical representation of aggregate medical parameters, such as the relevance of the research topic, objects and research methods, goals, and objectives of the thesis, blood volume, scientific novelty, practical significance, self-regulation and influence on the upper and inner parts of the heart.

Key words: Project Techreh, achievements in science, common vascular zone, self-regulation, effect on the upper and working heart, medical parameters, BITalino.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлен обзор математической модели системы кровообращения для сердечно-сосудистой системы с помощью BITalino и дано основа для математического представления совокупных медицинских параметров, таких как актуальность темы исследования, объекты и методы исследования, цели и задачи диссертации, объем крови,

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научная новизна, практическое значение, саморегуляция и влияние на верхние и внутренние отделы сердца.

Ключевые слова: Project Techreh, достижения науки, общая сосудистая зона, само регуляция, воздействие на верхние и работающие части сердце, медицинские показатели, BITalino.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada BITalino orqali yurak-qon tomir tizimi uchun qon aylanish tizimining matematik modelining umumiy ko'rinishini tavsiflaydi va tadqiqot mavzusining dolzarbligi, ob'ektlar va tadqiqot usullari, maqsadlari va vazifalari kabi umumiy tibbiy ko'rsatkichlarni matematik ifodalash uchun asos yaratadi. Dissertatsiya qon hajmi, ilmiy yangiligi, amaliy ahamiyati, o'z-o'zini tartibga solish va yurakning yuqori va ichki qismlariga ta'siri haqida gap boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Techreh loyihasi, fandagi yutuqlar, umumiy qon tomir zonasi, o'z-o'zini tartibga solish, yurakning yuqori va ish qismiga ta'siri, tibbiy ko'rsatkichlar, BITalino.

When TechRech project has established in the Karshi branch and organized meeting a round table discussed the questions connected with the development of educational content of the future master "Computer Systems in Medicine", the interaction between universities, and clarification of future work in Karshi. The overall Formative Program definition was discussed by all the Partners, and, in order to increase the number of participants to the course and to meet the Uzbekistan laws, and in accordance with EACEA Office, and the TechRech Steering Committee it was established the:

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Technologies a two-year Master "Computer Systems in Medicine". Indeed, due the national law, in Uzbekistan the master study should be at least 2 years, from which 1 year is dedicated to the Technology for Rehabilitation study unit;

(development of short courses for medical and technical professionals (TPMI).

During the research study of the project was recognized that in Uzbekistan there are huge demand for the short professional courses how to use technology in rehabilitation and overall in medicine. Thus, it was decided to develop short courses for medical professionals and technicians. The curricula definition of each Formative Programme action will be followed by development of the learning materials by the Partners and of an ICT platform for the dissemination of the didactic materials, contents, and project results. The aim of this publication is to present new teaching materials for study units of the short development courses —ICT in Medicine. In the present publication the TechReh project team developed and introduced several units for the organizing of the short professional development courses. For example, —New technologies in Medicine is dedicated to the modern technologies in rehabilitation.

This project shows amazing and excellent results who can be making a Ph.D. dissertation about medicine such as cardiology, bio signals, and illness of this specialty. In the laboratory used devise BITalino.

BITalino is an affordable & open-source bio signals platform designed for Education & Prototyping. This is the ideal toolkit to be used in laboratory & classroom environments or to create prototypes and applications using physiological sensors. BITalino (r)evolution is compatible with easy-to-use

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software (OpenSignals) & hardware blocks with sensors for electrocardiography (ECG).

I will invest and exchange my experience in technical innovations in healthcare and hospitals/ startup strategies of projects and entrepreneurship skills and use my passion for innovative solutions to bring more value to the mentorship. Our young team gives new ideas and scientific solving problems had departments of the local conference. My research topic about “Creation of a mathematical model and software for the pathology of the circulatory system in the cardiovascular system”. As a result, participating in meeting Tech Rech project I achieved more than what I dreamed about it. All the dissertations and scientists that they considered studied the creation of a mathematical model of blood circulation and what problems were raised. The relevance of the topic is sometimes that, from different pathologies, doctors can not put the diagnosis of the heart in circulation. Blood circulation is a unique system that has blood transport that runs there. In different pathologies, the heart and blood circulation give different results.

The implementation of this project includes the following tasks:

1. Analyzing of the results of a healthy person and the general type of all cardiovascular diseases in a narrow area and the study of the effect of covid 19 virus on the cardiovascular system.
2. Analyzing all mathematical models and consult with cardiologists on how to treat other diseases arising in the new era.
3. Developing a mobile cardiology application with the necessary tools for software and PC.

During my experience, I would gain and enjoy Tech Rech project and publishing

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articles Last year I was the winner of the competition “The best young scientist” 2020 - 2021 and “The best young teacher ” which is organized by “Bobek” in Central Asia.

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